

2-Phenyl-3-(4-methoxybenzamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (2): 1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) were reacted in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h, then the temperature was further raised to 180° for 30 min. The product was treated with ether and water to remove unreacted hydrazone and thiomalic acid. It was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (10%) and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from 95% ethanol (70%), m.p. 107° (Found: N, 7.12; S, 8.15. C₁₉H₁₈N₂O₅S requires N, 7.25; S, 8.29%).

Antimycobacterial activity: The antimycobacterial activity of compounds 1 and 2 was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium (5 ml). The retardation of the growth rate was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated with solvent (DMF) for control purposes. It has been concluded that all compounds (1 and 2) possess significant tuberculostatic activity at 30 µg ml⁻¹ concentration. The physical and biological data are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Sl no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**		
				µg ml ⁻¹		
				0	5	30
1.	C ₆ H ₅	210	84	+	+	-
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	152	88	+	+	-
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	122	86	+	+	-
4.	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	205	70	+	+	-
5.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	180	81	+	+	-
6.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	222	71	+	+	-
7.	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	162	68	+	+	-
8.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	185	72	+	+	-
9.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	235	79	+	+	-
10.	3,4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	254	74	+	+	-
11.	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	179	82	+	+	-
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	175	67	+	+	-
13.	3,5-Br ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	237	85	+	+	-

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, N, S analyses.

** + = No inhibition, - = active.

TABLE 2—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**		
				µg ml ⁻¹		
				0	5	30
1.	C ₆ H ₅	107	70	+	+	-
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	130	74	+	+	-
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	128	76	+	+	-
4.	CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	175	55	+	+	-
5.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	135	64	+	+	-
6.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	154	66	+	+	-
7.	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	115	65	+	+	-
8.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	166	62	+	+	-
9.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	142	61	+	+	-
10.	3,4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	113	69	+	+	-
11.	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	130	72	+	+	-
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	110	68	+	+	-
13.	3,5-Br ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	158	74	+	+	-

* and ** Explanations as in Table 1.

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Studies on Isoniazide Derivatives. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-3-(pyridylcarbonyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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ISONIAZIDE possess tuberculostatic activity¹. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various kinds of biological activities like hypnotic², anaesthetic³, antifungal⁴ etc. With a view to get more active drug, we have prepared 4-thiazolidinones of type 1 by the condensation of 4-substituted benzalisoniazides with thiomalic acid. 4-Substituted benzalisoniazides were obtained by condensing isoniazide with different aromatic aldehydes. The constitution was supported by ir spectra⁵⁻⁸. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones of type 1 were taken on KBr pellets and characterised; 1655 (C=O), 1580 (NCO) and 1600 nm (NH).

Experimental

4-Benzal isoniazide: Benzaldehyde (0.1 mol) was added to the solution of isoniazide (0.1 mol) in

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF 4-SUBSTITUTED-BENZALISONIAZIDES

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	% N : Found/(Calcd)	Zone of inhibition in mm		
						<i>S. aureus</i> (24 h)	<i>B. megaterium</i> (24 h)	<i>E. coli</i> (24 h)
1	Phenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	185	88	18.90 (18.67)	12	10	15
2	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	240	82	20.60 (20.74)	11	19	14
3	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	278	85	20.60 (20.74)	10	19	14
4	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ OCl	212	70	16.25 (16.18)	4	9	17
5	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ OCl	215	89	16.22 (16.18)	6	10	16
6	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	234	81	17.50 (17.42)	20	16	14
7	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	228	76	17.50 (17.42)	4	10	12
8	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	280	74	17.45 (17.42)	2	8	11
9	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂ Br	275	82	18.00 (18.12)	14	24	21
10	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	214	83	10.50 (10.53)	14	22	31
11	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	232	78	15.46 (15.50)	24	9	16
12	5-Bromo-4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ Br	262	88	12.11 (12.00)	25	28	25
13	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	245	74	16.40 (16.47)	15	14	24
14	Cinnamyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	195	76	16.75 (16.78)	20	15	12
15	α -Furyl	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	210	70	19.52 (19.53)	15	14	12

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (I)

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	N % : Found/(Calcd.)	Zone of inhibition in mm		
						<i>S. aureus</i> (24 h)	<i>B. megaterium</i> (24 h)	<i>E. coli</i> (24 h)
1	Phenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	150	52	11.90 (11.76)	14	19	17
2	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	195	55	13.95 (13.98)	12	22	18
3	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	187	50	13.96 (13.98)	12	24	20
4	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	225	61	10.75 (10.73)	8	18	22
5	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	186	59	10.75 (10.73)	11	13	18
6	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	187	59	11.24 (11.26)	22	17	14
7	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	167	55	11.38 (11.26)	10	10	16
8	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	200	56	11.20 (11.26)	8	10	11
9	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SBr	177	53	9.50 (9.29)	20	34	31
10	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ SBr ₂	165	60	8.00 (7.90)	21	32	41
11	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	198	59	10.51 (10.42)	24	11	20
12	5-Bromo-4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ SBr	105	51	8.75 (8.71)	19	33	35
13	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	160	47	11.40 (11.32)	20	18	28
14	Cinnemyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	170	63	11.00 (10.97)	26	20	22
15	α -Furyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	155	45	12.25 (12.10)	21	21	21

methanol (25 ml) and refluxed for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol (88%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 69.50; H, 4.75; N, 18.90). C₁₃H₁₁N₃O requires C, 69.33; H, 4.88; N, 18.67%. Similarly, 4-substituted benzalisoniazides were prepared (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(p-pyridylcarbonyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones: 4-Benzalisoniazide (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min°. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from ethanol (52%), m.p. 150° (Found: C, 57.20; H, 4.45; N, 11.90). C₁₇H₁₆N₃O₄S requires C, 57.14; H, 4.20; N, 11.76%. Similarly, 4-substituted benzalisoniazides were treated with thiomalic acid (Table 2).

Antimicrobial screening: The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup-plate¹⁰ method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus* and *B. megaterium* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded.

The condensation products with thiomalic acid are more active as compared to that of 4-substituted benzalisoniazide. Bromophenol residue enhances the activity against *B. megaterium* and *E. coli*.

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Amidomethylation of 5/6-Nitrobenzimidazole. Synthesis and Biological Activities of Certain 1-(N-Alkyl/Arylamidomethyl)-6-nitrobenzimidazoles†

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THE syntheses of several types of amidomethyl compounds including their varied biological and pharmacological activities have been reported in recent years¹⁻⁵. It has also been a fact that the benzimidazole moiety itself is a formidable pharmacophore and it is still more so with a nitro substituent at 5/6-position⁶. Therefore, in continuation of our studies on aminomethylation and amidomethylations of benzimidazoles⁷⁻⁹, it was desirable to conduct amidomethylations on 5/6-nitrobenzimidazole and to determine the structure, orientation and pharmacological efficacy of the products.

Scheme 1

5/6-Nitrobenzimidazole (2, Scheme 1) has been synthesised for the purpose from 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (1) by a standard method¹⁰. Compound 2 has been condensed with paraformaldehyde and various carboxamides (3) separately in ethanol adopting a modified Einhorn-Tsherniac procedure to get a single product in each case. The compounds have been purified by column chromatography using alumina (neutral) as an adsorbent and characterised by their analytical and spectral data (Table 1) as 1-(*N*-alkyl/arylamidomethyl)-5/6-nitrobenzimidazoles (4/5), in view of the possible tautomerism of compound 2.

It has been suggested that benzimidazole (2) reacts first with formaldehyde to give the benzimidazole-1-methylol which subsequently loses a water

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